

The revised SUPERBLINK-GAIA catalog of stars with proper motion larger than 40 mas/yr

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Abstract

Abstract. We examine the astrometric measurements and physical properties of 2.5 million stars with proper motions larger than 40 mas/yr, which were originally charted in the SUPERBLINK proper motion catalog, and for which data from the GAIA second release (GAIA DR2) is now available. These represent the stars with the fastest proper motions observed by GAIA, the vast majority of which consist of low-mass K and M dwarfs in the vicinity of the Sun ($d < 200$ pc). We find that the GAIA proper motions are in excellent agreement with the SUPERBLINK values, and show how the new GAIA parallaxes and optical magnitudes significantly enhance the all-sky census of faint stars with large proper motions.

1 Introduction

The SUPERBLINK catalog (Lépine & Shara 2005, Lépine & Gaidos 2011) identifies stars with large proper motions ($\mu > 40$ mas/yr) over most of the sky. This poster investigates the recovery of those high proper motion stars in the Second Data Release of the GAIA catalog.

2 SUPERBLINK stars recovered in GAIA

We cross-matched the SUPERBLINK catalog of 2.5 million stars with proper motions $\mu > 40$ mas/yr with the GAIA DR2 release, and found matches for 99.6% of the sources. We recover GAIA parallaxes (ϖ_G) and proper motions (μ_G) for all stars, along with GAIA magnitudes (G, G_{BP}, G_{RP}). Fig.1 plots the subset of 570,119 stars with proper motions $\mu > 80$ mas/yr. Only 2,332 SUPERBLINK stars do not have counterparts in GAIA DR2; these stars tend to be concentrated in two areas on the sky, which suggest GAIA survey completeness issues. Fig.2 compares the SUPERBLINK proper motion values to those from GAIA, which show excellent agreement. The scatter in the proper motion differences in R.A. and Decl. is consistent with the ± 8 mas/yr errors advertised for the SUPERBLINK survey.

Fig.3 shows a reduced proper motion diagram of the SUPERBLINK stars recovered in GAIA, with the proper motion and magnitudes from GAIA DR2. It is easy to split the low-mass stars from the local disk (lower velocity) and halo (higher velocity) populations. Those stars are represented by red dots (disk) and blue dots (halo) throughout the rest of the figures. An HR diagram (Fig.4) shows that the two populations (disk, halo) occupy very distinct loci, as expected from their different metallicity levels, which significantly affects the $G_{BP} - G_{RP}$ color term.

The SUPERBLINK catalog already provided photometric counterparts in a variety of other catalogs, including infrared magnitudes from 2MASS, and ultraviolet magnitudes from GALEX, whenever the star was detected in those bands. We plot in Fig.5 an HR diagram generated using the $NUV - G$ ultraviolet-to-optical color; active stars as well as stars with

white dwarf companions show up with significantly blue $NUV - G$ terms for a given value of absolute magnitude M_G . Fig.6 is an HR diagram generated using the $J - K$ infrared color term from 2MASS, which also hints at metallicity effects on $J - K$.

To investigate survey range and completeness, we calculate stellar distances d from the reported GAIA parallax using $d = \varpi_G^{-1}$, and transverse motions V_T from GAIA parallaxes and proper motion using $V_T = 4.74 \mu_G \varpi_G^{-1}$. Results are shown in Fig.7. Stars from the two different populations are shown in different colors: low-velocity / Galactic disk stars in red, and high-velocity / Galactic disk stars in blue. Disk stars clearly dominate at smaller distances; halo stars only show up in significant numbers at large distances, and we can thank the proper motion selection for identifying them. We plot in Fig.8 the absolute G magnitude as a function of calculated distance d . This illustrates how the magnitude limit of the SUPERBLINK catalog (and that of GAIA as well) introduces significant limitations on the range over which low luminosity stars can be detected. This is especially critical for halo stars, since their relative scarcity in the Solar vicinity means they are mainly detected at larger distances.

3 Conclusions

We find that GAIA has done an excellent job at identifying high proper motion stars ($> 99\%$ success) at least down to the magnitude limit of the SUPERBLINK catalog ($G=20$). This exercise illustrates the potential for identifying large numbers of low-mass disk and halo stars with GAIA, although their identification will be limited in distance (a few hundred parsecs or less in some cases). The GAIA parallaxes combined with photometric data from other catalogs (notably 2MASS, GALEX) promise to significantly improve our characterization of these objects.

References

- Lépine, S., & Shara, M. M. 2005, AJ, 129, 1483
Lépine, S., & Gaidos, E. M. 2011, AJ, 142, 138

Figure 1: Sky distribution of the subset of 570,119 SUPERBLINK stars with proper motions $\mu > 80$ mas/yr, the vast majority of which are recovered in the Gaia Second Data Release (black dots). However, 2,332 stars with $\mu > 80$ mas/yr are currently not recovered as high proper motions stars by Gaia (red dots). The zone south of Decl. $=-30^\circ$ is known to be incomplete in the SUPERBLINK catalog for this proper motion range; the catalog is however complete in the south for $\mu > 120$ mas/yr.

Figure 2: Comparison of proper motion values for the 2,586,815 stars in common between the SUPERBLINK and Gaia surveys, in the zone north of Decl. $=-30^\circ$. Left: Comparison of the total proper motions: 92.1% of the stars have values that agree to within ± 25 mas/yr (red lines). Right: proper motion differences in the direction of R.A. and Decl., plotted as a function of the Gaia magnitude G . Red brackets show the mean and 1σ dispersion as a function of magnitude. In the $12 < G < 17$ magnitude range, proper motions generally agree to ± 8 mas/yr, confirming the previous estimate for the proper motion precision of the SUPERBLINK survey.

Figure 3: Reduced Proper Motion Diagram of the SUPERBLINK stars with Gaia matches, used to select two local populations of low-mass stars. In red: the low-velocity low-mass stars, typically metal-rich K and M dwarfs (Galactic disk). And in blue: the high velocity low-mass stars, typically metal poor K and M subdwarfs (Galactic halo).

Figure 5: Ultra-violet to optical HR diagram of the SUPERBLINK stars with Gaia matches. NUV magnitudes are obtained from cross-match to the GALEX catalog. Many low-mass stars from both the disk and halo populations show significant NUV excess, resulting in blue NUV-G colors. These are either active, or have white dwarf companions.

Figure 4: Optical HR diagram of the SUPERBLINK stars with Gaia matches, with the same color scheme as figure 3. The local metalpoor halo stars stand out as being significantly bluer in GBP - GRP color. This demonstrates the very high sensitivity of GBP - GRP colors to K/M dwarf metallicities.

Figure 6: Infrared/optical HR diagram of the SUPERBLINK stars with Gaia matches. Infrared J and K magnitudes are obtained from cross-match to the 2MASS catalog. Lowmass stars show a broad range of J-K colors, which may be correlated with metallicity. However J-K color does not appear to be a good metallicity indicator.

Figure 7: Range in distance and transverse velocity of the SUPERBLINK/Gaia stars using the same color scheme as above. The sample is range-limited because of the (deliberate) proper motion limit ($\mu > 40$ mas/yr). This limits the stars from the local Galactic Disk population to only the nearest objects, but includes large numbers of stars from the local Galactic Halo population, which constitutes the strength of this high-proper motion selection.

Figure 8: Range in distance and absolute magnitude of the SUPERBLINK/Gaia stars, using the same color scheme as above. The sample is range-limited due to the magnitude limit of Gaia ($G=20$). This mostly affects the luminosity range of the Galactic halo subset. Deeper surveys (e.g. Pan-STARRS, LSST) will be needed to identify larger numbers of lower-mass, low-luminosity stars from the local halo population.